

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART IV. N¹-AND
N⁴-SUBSTITUTED SULPHANILAMIDES, ACYCLIC ACYL
DERIVATIVES OF SULPHATHIAZOLE
AND SULPHAPYRIDINE

BY K. R. DORASWAMY AND P. C. GUHA

Sixteen aliphatic acyl derivatives of sulphapyridine and sulphathiazole have been prepared.

Although Fournau *et al* (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1936, 122, 258) announced in 1936, that the therapeutic activity of sulphanilamide was greatly reduced by the introduction of an acyl group on the 4-amino nitrogen, several investigations (Buttle and Gray, *Lancet* 1936, I, 1296; Adams, Long and Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2342, 2346; Trefouel, Nitti, *et al.*, *Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1937, 58, 30) have been undertaken on the synthesis and therapeutic evaluation of the N⁴-acyl derivatives. Three years after this announcement, Miller, Rock and Moore (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1198) by a systematic study of the N⁴-acyl derivatives of sulphanilamide found that the caproyl derivative was as effective as sulphanilamide itself and also less toxic. They found that (i) the monocarboxylic acid derivatives were more effective than those of the dicarboxylic acids; (ii) among the monocarboxylic acid derivatives the activity increased with the increase in length of the acyl groups up to 6-carbon atoms, after which it decreased rapidly; and that (iii) the *normal*-acyl derivatives were more active than the corresponding *iso*-derivatives. Generally all these investigators found that the toxicity of the acyl derivatives was much lower than that of sulphanilamide.

The long-chain fatty acids, particularly those derived from chaulmoogra and hydnocarpus oils, have been successfully used in the treatment of leprosy and tuberculosis. So, it was expected that the range of therapeutic usefulness of the acyl sulphanilamides derived from these fatty acids would be extended further to include these acid-fast mycobacteria, viz. those of tubercular and leprous bacilli. With this end in view, Bargmann and Hesselberg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2243) and Rajagopalan (*Curr. Sci.*, 1942, 11, 394) have synthesised some N⁴-acyl derivatives from straight chain fatty acids, the therapeutic properties of which have not yet been reported.

The presence of the grouping H₂N. C₆H₄. SO₂NH- is considered to be of fundamental physiological significance from the standpoint of the existing theories of the mode of action of sulphanilamide drugs, and any stable structural alteration in this group has been known to destroy the therapeutic activity. So, it may be thought that the N⁴-acyl derivatives may not possess any therapeutic activity at all on the ground that the amino group is blocked in their molecules. However, it is known that some of the acyl derivatives of sulphanilamide are hydrolysed *in vivo* to the respective sulphanilamide (Kohl and Flynn, *Proc. Soc. Biol. Med.*, 1940, 44, 445; Bradbury and Jordan, *Biochem J.*, 1942, 36, 287). So it may be expected that the N⁴-acyl derivatives of sulphapyridine and sulphathiazole will

possibly undergo the cleavage giving rise to the original sulphathiazole or sulphapyridine *in vivo*. Further, in such liberation of the parent compound *in vivo*, in addition to the sulphanilamide, simultaneously the fatty acids also will be liberated. So it was thought to be of interest to ascertain whether the presence of these fatty acids will have any influence on the therapeutic activity of the free amino compound.

While numerous acyl derivatives of sulphanilamide have been prepared, no systematic study seems to have been made on the acyl derivatives of sulphapyridine and sulphathiazole. Considerations such as these led to the synthesis of the N⁴-acyl derivatives of sulphapyridine and sulphathiazole from the following fatty acids: formic, acetic, propionic, butyric, isovaleric, caprylic, nonylic and capric. The caproic and heptonic acids were not available in these laboratories, and so the derivatives corresponding to those acids could not be studied.

The preparation of these acyl derivatives is usually effected by the action of acid chlorides or anhydrides (or in some cases, the acids themselves) on sulphanilamide. In the present work, however, mostly acid chlorides were employed, the formyl derivative having been prepared from ethyl formate. The acid chlorides were prepared by the action of thionyl chloride on the acids. The reaction between the acid chlorides and the sulphapyridine (or sulphathiazole) was carried out in boiling pyridine solution. The reaction mixture on treatment with excess of water gave the acyl derivatives, which were purified by precipitation by acid from their dilute sodium hydroxide solution and further by recrystallisation from alcohol.

The melting points of these acyl derivatives are not sharp in spite of repeated crystallisations. They are all white amorphous powders, sparingly soluble in water. The result of their pharmacological examination is eagerly awaited.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The formyl derivatives were prepared by refluxing sulphathiazole or sulphapyridine with excess of ethyl formate. On refluxing for 4 to 5 hours the sulphathiazole (or sulphapyridine) gradually dissolved giving rise to a pale red solution. The excess of ethyl formate was removed by evaporation, and the solid left behind was washed with water and alcohol, and purified by crystallisation from alcohol.

The other acyl derivatives were prepared by the following general method described for propionylsulphathiazole.

Preparation of Propionylsulphathiazole.

Sulphathiazole (1g.) was dissolved in pyridine and propionyl chloride (1 c. c.) was added. The mixture was heated under reflux for about 1 hour and the resulting product on dilution with excess of water gave the acyl derivative.

This was filtered and purified by dissolving in sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitating by acidification. The precipitated product was filtered off, washed with water and alcohol, dried and weighed (1.2 g.), m. p. 245°.

TABLE I

R.	Acid used.	Acyl derivatives of sulphathiazole.		Acyl derivatives of sulphapyridine.	
		M.p.	Nitrogen % Found. Theo :	M.p.	Nitrogen % Found. Theo :
H	Formic	215°	15.04 14.84	205°	15.33 15.16
CH ₃ -	Acetic	256°	225°
CH ₃ .CH ₂ -	Propionic	245°	12.98 13.50	217°	14.13 13.77
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ -	Butyric	250°	13.04 12.92	165°	12.31 12.16
CH ₃ } CH ₃ } CH . CH ₃	<i>iso</i> Valeric	180°	12.47 12.39	191-2°	13.03 12.61
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₆	Caprylic	214°	11.28 11.08	210°	11.33 11.20
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₇	Nonylic	189°	10.71 10.63	186°	11.01 10.80
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₈	Capric	142°	10.37 10.27	160°	10.15 10.42

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

Received March 1, 1946.

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART V. N¹-AND N⁴-SUBSTITUTED SULPHANILAMIDES. N⁴-ISO CYCLIC ACYL DERIVATIVES OF SULPHATHIAZOLE AND SULPHAPYRIDINE

BY K. R. DORASWAMY AND P. C. GUHA

Sixteen *iso*-cyclic acyl derivatives of sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine have been prepared.

Although much work has been done on the study of the N⁴-acyclic acyl derivatives of sulphanilamides, it is surprising that only a very few derivatives from aromatic acids have been reported so far and among them only the *p*-nitrobenzoyl derivative is reported to be as active as sulphanilamide itself, and the benzoyl derivative is reported to be inactive. Further, no corresponding derivatives of sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine have so far been made. Therefore, it was considered worth while to prepare a few derivatives of these two drugs with some very common aromatic acids.

These acyl derivatives were prepared by the action of the appropriate acid chloride on sulphathiazole or sulphapyridine in aqueous alkaline solution. The acid chlorides required for this work were prepared by the action of thionyl chloride on the corresponding acids without the use of a solvent. The condensation products were purified by crystallisation from alcohol. They are usually colourless amorphous powders, without sharp melting point and low solubility in water. Their pharmacological examination is awaited.